

Exploring the application of Smart Tourism technologies in Smart Destinations considering the Viable Systems Approach

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Abstract

Incorporating smart technology within highly visited tourist attractions is a relatively new trend in the tourism sector that aims to enhance travelers' satisfaction by offering particular and customized services. Tourists, service suppliers, and DMOs are just a few significant players that stand to benefit from using smart technologies in tourism destinations. The fundamental goal of smart tourism is to make destinations more competitive while positively impacting society, the environment, and the economy. The new foundational elements of smart tourism are value co-creation and the sharing of resources, which are grounded in Service-Dominant Logic and the Viable Systems Approach. By considering tourists as actively involved in making experiences unique and unforgettable, we may use SDL and VSA as novel viewpoints. Accordingly, we can improve the prospect of satisfied and loyal visitors by making high-quality impressions on them through co-creating memorable experiences. Thus, this extended abstract presents an inquiry that examines the contributions of smart technologies in creating smart tourism destinations from the viewpoint of the Viable Systems Approach. The findings imply that the VSA provides opportunities for evaluating viability and sustainability through smart destinations and planning and organizing smart tourist ecosystems.

Keywords: Smart tourism, Smart technology, Viable systems approach, Service-dominant logic, Sustainability.

1. Introduction

Many destinations embrace smart tourism by augmenting their businesses through networked technology systems that facilitate instantaneous exchange of information among all stakeholders (Buhalis & Amaranggana, 2014). Innovative tourism offerings are centered on smart system strategies to improve the tourism industry or particular locations (Chuang, 2023). Using the unique capabilities of smart technologies, smart tourism, which is usually implemented at the destination stage, strives to achieve development goals (Gretzel, 2021). Service-Dominant Logic provides an

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empirical structure that can aid tourism businesses in differentiating themselves from the competition while developing novel tourist offerings and improving value activities through co-creation (Blazquez-Resino et al., 2015). The all-encompassing viewpoint of the Viable Systems Approach also makes it possible to acknowledge the phenomenon's complexity (Barile et al., 2017). A viable systems evaluation of a tourist ecosystem uncovers a relationship that links all system components together by transitioning to a more holistic view of system viability (Iandolo et al., 2019). So, this extended abstract aims to study the smart tourism technologies applied in smart tourism by highlighting the significant role of the Viable Systems approach.

2. Smart Tourism Destinations

Many cities serve as major tourist attractions, and smart cities are leading the charge for innovative tourism applications (Wang et al., 2022). The intelligence level of cities is a good indicator of the smartness level of destinations, often located in metropolitan regions (Gretzel et al., 2016). An information-based or smart tourist destination uses ICT to speed up information and knowledge sharing that is relevant to tourists (Jovicic, 2019). Smart tourism destinations are those that make use of modern technology to help businesses and tourists work together for the benefit of both parties (Boes et al., 2015). Travelers can now access information from any location anytime via their smartphones or other portable devices, thanks to cloud services such as HearPlanet, TripAdvisor, and Tripcast (Jovicic, 2019). Smart destinations allow destination marketing organizations to (re)establish themselves in key roles related to coordinating, facilitating, and governing (Gretzel & Scarpino-Johns, 2018). For instance, the governments of China, South Korea, and Spain have developed initiatives with this objective and models for STD management and execution over the past ten years (Muniz et al., 2021).

3. Smart Tourism Technologies

The competitiveness and approach taken by tourist organizations and destinations are defined by technological breakthroughs, which have entirely revolutionized tourism (Buhalis, 2020). The technologies that directly support smart tourist experiences include the Internet of Things, mobile devices, cloud computing, QR codes, location-based services, recommendation systems, GIS, and virtual reality/augmented virtual reality (Akdu, 2020). By utilizing AI to take advantage of the compatibility and interconnection of various technologies, smart tourism provides the informatics foundation needed for value co-creation (Junqueiro et al., 2022). **Figure 1** shows how all parties

involved can co-create value by integrating smart technologies, which improves destination management and the overall experience (Femenia-Serra & Ivars-Baidal, 2021).

Fig. 1. Intelligent Environment in Tourism (Source: Buhalis, 2020)

4. Smart Tourism and Viable Systems Approach

Service-Dominant Logic (SDL) is a theoretical framework that examines the importance of service supply, which is seen as a pathway defined by systemic qualities and characterized by constant change (Iandolo et al., 2019). It is necessary to simultaneously look at a smart tourism ecosystem from two distinct points to consider it a viable system: the steady and the dynamic, the structure and the system, and the decision and the action. The decision-maker's ability to build harmonious associations (consonance) with the items in the same context keeps the system alive. Therefore, choices need to be based on an interactive approach that can push people toward a common goal. The search for ventures that share the same objective (the resonance effect) is one of the most essential steps in going beyond the boundaries of a purely operational view (**Figure 2**) (Iandolo et al., 2019). By combining the ideas of viability and sustainability, the viable smart tourism focuses on the point at which the decision-makers free will is shown: the change from a broad structure to a specific structure (Iandolo et al., 2019). The ultimate goal of STE could be to create technology-enhanced experiences that make destinations more competitive and give them a long-term competitive edge (Polese et al., 2018).

Fig. 2. Integrating value co-creation, viability and sustainability (Source: Iandolo et al., 2019)

5. Concluding remarks

Sustainable tourism can be developed with the help of ICTs that enhance visitor engagement and information sharing. The spread of digital knowledge has led to the emergence of "smart destinations," in which everyone interested has convenient knowledge acquisition that can be employed to recover the services and procedures in the future. Savvy travelers prefer information availability to arrange their trips online and analyze the tourism sector before their trips. Efficacious management of tourist attractions, personalized trip planning, ingenious safety procedures, and comfortable journeys are other components of smart tourism. By strengthening the experience of tourists, increasing the productivity and competitiveness of enterprises and destinations, and creating new opportunities for services and markets to grow, smart tourism technologies could eventually make the tourism industry more viable. The S-D Logic framework projects the procedure that encourages visitors to enthusiastically engage in creating their impressions. The Viable Systems approach necessitates the examination of various information sources, though holding onto an integrative perspective due to the complexity of shared attitudes and local decision-making procedures.

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